

DEVELOPMENT OF COORDINATION SKILLS IN FIGURE SKATING

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Modern figure skating makes high demands on athletes' physical fitness. In this regard, achieving high sports results implies constant improvement of physical abilities and efficiency of technical and tactical actions. One of the promising ways to solve these problems is to improve coordination skills. At first glance, assessing the situation in the theory and practice of this issue, one gets the impression that everything is clear and everything has already been studied. This topic is dedicated to the works of the influential scientists of our time - Bernstein N.A., Anokhin P.K., Matveev L.P., Lyakh V.I., Zaporozhanov V.A.

In modern sports theory, it is customary to distinguish specific, special and general coordination skills.

The reason for the emergence of certain (personal) coordination abilities is the uneven development of psychophysiological functions that ensure the processes of coordination of actions. The most important specific coordination skills are the ability to accurately distinguish, evaluate and measure the temporal, spatial and power parameters of movements: balance, rhythm, quick response, orientation in space, rapid reshaping of motor activity, voluntary muscle relaxation, vestibular stability, etc.

Special coordination skills - these are capabilities that determine a person's readiness to optimally regulate and control motor actions similar to their structure. Special coordination ability of figure skaters describes indicators of efficiency, versatility and reliability of performing figure skating technique (for example, turns, braking, skating in different directions, transition from simple running forward to backward running, comfortable and uncomfortable throwing, complex perform items). In addition, there are elementary and complex coordination skills, which obviously have a different structure of control and execution. Now beginners are shown in the process of simple motor movements, such as walking and running, elementary elements, and complex ones in movement art and sports games. A relatively elementary form includes a clear repetition of the spatial parameters of movements; rapid reshaping of motor actions in conditions of sudden changes in the situation is more complicated.

Coordination skills in figure skating are closely related to other physical skills: speed, strength, flexibility, as well as game techniques and tactics. Therefore,

explicit (absolute) and hidden (relative or partial) indicators of coordination ability were introduced. The first describes the level of development of the coordination skills of this athlete, without taking into account the speed, strength and other capabilities of this athlete. Relative ones are aimed at assessing the level of coordination skills taking into account these possibilities. Due to the diversity of specific coordination abilities, many absolute and relative indicators of coordination abilities can be used.

The main methods of assessment of coordination skills are as follows: observation method, test, expert assessment and instrumental methods. Both physical tests and psychodiagnostic tests are used to measure coordination skills in sports practice.

The most important aspect in the selection of control exercises for assessment of coordination skills is their theoretical basis. However, in sports practice, especially in figure skating, it is not unusual to use such tests without any scientific basis. Such behavior of "experts" cannot be considered correct. "Firstly, it is impossible to get a clear, differentiated assessment of the level of individual development with the help of one, even very complex (complex) test, which includes many motor tasks. Secondly, one or more, although informative, based on the test results 'ra, as we know, it is illegal to estimate the level of formation of all KQ without exception, the number of which is very large.

Based on this, V. I. Lyakh developed a minimum permissible battery of 5 tests, which allows to fully and informatively determine the level of development of coordination ability. The presented control exercises make it possible to determine the relative and absolute indicators of coordination ability related to different groups of motor movements:

Shuttle running at a distance of 3x10 meters - Stopwatch or time counting system; Straight roads 30 and 10 meters long, bordered by two parallel lines; behind each line of the 10-meter segment - 2 semicircles with a radius of 50 cm centered on the line;

Control of the ability to maintain body balance (equilibrium) - checking static-dynamic balance: A simple way to monitor the body's ability to maintain balance is the static-dynamic balance test developed in North America. A stopwatch and a balance board are required for the test (Figure 4). There are many types of them, although the principle of operation is similar everywhere. Regardless of which company's balancing board is used, the same thing is basically used in replication studies.

Control of coordination of movements - Y Balance Test Station: This is a dynamic test performed in a single leg position (Figure 3), which places high demands on strength and coordination skills, flexibility and proprioception. This method is used to control coordination skills, symmetry in movements, and also determines the level of risk of injury to the lower extremities. The test includes an assessment of the amplitude of movements in three directions: forward, posterior-internal, posterior-lateral. Goal: demonstrate maximum possible range of motion (flexibility) with the other leg while balancing on one leg while moving the measuring platform smoothly. The subject makes three attempts with each leg in all directions. The result is measured in centimeters.

Summary: There are several other sets of such exercises in figure skaters. The main reason for choosing these exercises is that they can be used to determine coordination ability in other sports. In order to develop the coordination ability, it is necessary to be fed with constant training, for those who have just started playing sports and those who have been playing sports for several years, there is

a deficiency in this ability, therefore, frequent test tests to determine the level of KQ it is recommended to be taken.

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